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Sex Ratio In Haryana: Recent Trends And Inherent Contradictions

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Abstract

Generally it is said that economic growth enhances the social development, but is it true in case of Haryana? Per capita income of Haryana is the highest but social indicators are poor. This paper analyses the trends in the sex ratio in Haryana. Analyzing the census of India and the National Family Health Survey, from 2001-2011 census data, we found that adult sex ratio has increased while child sex ratio decreased. The main objective of this research is to evaluate imbalance in sex ratio and the inherent contradictions in it. The state of Haryana that have highest literacy rate has the most adverse female sex ratio and vice-versa. This paper also shows that some of the south Indian states like Kerala, Tamilnadu etc that have higher literacy rate than Haryana, have higher sex ratio as compared to Haryana.

Key-Words: Census of India, Son Preference, Sex Ratio of Haryana.

Introduction

From Haryana existence as a characteristic periphery to a more developed region before its formation in 1966, the state of Haryana has come a long way. It has emerged as one of the economically developed state of Indian Union with per capita income of Rs.62927 at 2004-05 prices in 2011-12 in comparison to Rs.38005/average for the country. But, In Haryana various social economic, demographic indicator provide evidences of gender bias and inequity against girls. Sex ratio is one of the important indicator to measure the extent of equity between male and female in a society at given point of time and also an important source to comprehend women's health and position in any society. Many studies in Haryana shows that female ratio in total population had always remained unfavourable. Survival of girl child in many districts of Haryana is a critical issue. Although according to census of India 2011 a little bit improvement shown in Haryana sex ratio over the last census 2001. But more strong efforts are necessary for the uplifting of the girls ratio in Haryana.

What is Sex Ratio?

1. It is a tool to determine gender equity of the population.
2. In India, It is defined as the number of female per 1000 males in the population.

Trends in sex ratio in Haryana:

1. Historically sex ratio in Haryana as remained imbalance to males.
2. Sex ratio of total population has seen upward surge in the last census.
3. In 2011 Census, sex ratio in India increased to 940 from 934 recorded in 2001 Census.

The Deficit of Girls:

The natural or normal sex ratios at birth are found to lie between 943 and 971 female per 1000 males. On this basis, the average figure worked out to 953 females per 1000 male

children (Rethorford and Roy, 2003, United Nations, 1998; Arnold et al., 2002). The shortfall of girls in respect of boy is calculated as per the sex ratio at birth. For the country as a whole, this figure worked out to 953 girls per 1000 boys. Anything below this figure would give the actual deficit. To see the regional variations in girl deficit in Haryana aggregate figure given for all districts. Mostly districts in the Haryana region are affecting in deficit of girls. Haryana have 877 sex ratio.

Table 1: Comparative sex Ratio, Child Sex Ratio of Haryana Districts: 2001 & 2011.

State/District	Sex-Ratio		Percent 0-6 pop		Sex-Ratio 0-6 Pop	
	2001	2011	2001	2011	2001	2011
Haryana	861	877	15.8	13.8	819	830
Panchkula	863	870	14.1	11.7	829	850
Ambala	868	882	13.2	10.9	782	807
Yamunanagar	862	877	14.4	11.8	806	825
Kurukshetra	866	889	14.2	12.0	771	817
Kaithal	853	880	15.4	12.6	799	821
Karnal	865	886	15.1	12.9	809	820
Panipat	829	861	16.4	13.7	809	833
Sonapat	839	853	15.4	12.7	788	790
Jind	852	890	15.8	12.4	818	835
Fatehabad	884	903	16.1	12.6	828	845
Sirsa	882	896	15.0	11.9	817	852
Hisar	851	871	15.5	12.1	832	849
Bhiwani	879	884	15.7	12.6	841	831
Rohtak	847	868	14.5	11.9	799	807
Jhajjar	847	861	15.0	12.1	801	774
Mahendragarh	918	814	15.2	12.5	811	784
Rewari	889	898	15.2	12.5	811	784
Gurgaon	850	853	15.5	13.1	807	826
Mewat	899	906	25.1	22.3	893	903
Faridabad	826	871	15.8	13.2	847	842
Palwal	862	879	20.0	16.5	854	862

Source census of India

International Reference

Table 2: Highest And Lowest Sex Ratio Districts Of Haryana

Sr.N.	District	Sex ratio
1	Mewat	906
2	Fatehabad	903
3	Rewari	898
4	Sirsa	896
5	Mahendragarh	894

Sr.N.	District	Sex Ratio
1	Gurgaon	853
2	Sonapat	853
3	Panipat	861
4	Jhajjar	861
5	Rohatak	868

Review of Literature:

On global scale, a number of studies have been documented by various scholars on patterns, trends, and determinants of declining child sex ratio in India (Chakraborty and Sinha, 2006; Deolalikar *et al.*, 2009; Unisha, 2009, etc.). But on regional scale, especially in case of Haryana, only a few studies like Sangwan and Sangwan (2012) have focused their attention on declining child sex ratio and its aftereffects on the socio-cultural milieu of society. The present study has endeavoured, therefore, to examine the patterns, trends, and determinants of declining child sex ratio and its implications in the state.

Identification of a Problem:

1. Impact of population policies on Sex Ratio.
2. Economic consideration associated with daughter favoritism against female in society.
3. Social insecurity for women.
4. Low literacy ratio in rural areas females.

Objective of Study:

The main objective of this Paper is find out imbalance in sex ratio and the inherent contradictions in it.

Research Methodology:

This Paper based on secondary data and information has been sourced from various books, journals, newspaper etc and research is descriptive in nature.

Implication and Suggestion:

1. Increase in the literacy rate.
2. Give respect to Females.
3. Recognize the economic contribution of women.

4. Stop emerging baby business.
5. Provide equal chances for women achieving job.
6. Protection for girls in modernization.
7. Stop female foeticide.

Conclusion:

The conclusion of this paper make known that besides of the carious legal law's and women's specific development programmed, the child sex ratio still continue in Haryana. The continuously declining child sex ratio is a example of gender bias in Haryana districts. The government of Haryana need to open the centers that provide education about the need of girl child and their participation in the national growth. Many seminar and workshop to be held time to time in rural areas. Need to increase the literacy ratio that help people to understand the importance of female in the today era. Without the improvement of the standard of female the country can't get success. People need to understand that the son and the daughter have equal in the society. Stop son preference, stop female foeticide and help to remove gender bias.

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